

Effect of *Urtica Dioica* and *Camellia Sinensis* on Rooster Reproductive and Testicular Traits

Emad Abdulgabbar Ali ✉

Asst. Prof., Dept. Anim. Prod., Colle. Agri, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Ali Sabah Al-Hassani

Prof., Dept. Anim. Prod., Colle. Agri. Engin. Sci., University of Baghdad, Iraq

Nihad Abdul-Lateef Ali

Prof., Dept. Anim. Prod., Colle. Agri, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Article History:

Received: 20.08.2025 Revised: 22.09.2025 Accepted: 24.09.2025 Published: 25.09.2025

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effects of varying dosages of *Urtica dioica* (nettle) leaf powder and *Camellia sinensis* (white tea) powder on the reproductive and histological characteristics of rooster testes. Conducted at the College of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Green University, over a 42-day period, the experiment involved 21 roosters at 45 weeks of age, which were randomly assigned to seven treatment groups with three replicates each. The treatment groups included: a standard diet without any additives as the control; a standard diet supplemented with 100 mg/kg or 150 mg/kg of white tea powder; a standard diet supplemented with 100 mg/kg, 150 mg/kg, or 200 mg/kg of nettle leaf powder. The results demonstrated significant improvements in sperm concentration, osmotic resistance, ejaculate volume, and individual sperm motility in certain groups receiving white tea and nettle leaf powders.

Keywords: *Andrology, Antioxidants, Endocrinology, Testosterone, Fertility.*

Suggested citation: Ali, E.A., Al-Hassani, A.S., & Ali, N. A.-L. (2025). Effect of *Urtica Dioica* and *Camellia Sinensis* on Rooster Reproductive and Testicular Traits. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(5), 128-137. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(5\).14](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(5).14)

Introduction

Histological changes during certain seasons cause many wild bird species to undergo testicular regression, leading to a complete cessation of sperm production (Abbas, et al., 2019). In contrast, domestic birds have been selectively bred for traits such as meat production, and their testicular development is limited primarily by factors such as age and illness, rather than environmental influences (Wang, & Ho, 2009). Since the number of fertilized eggs directly impacts the profitability of laying hens, the primary objective in poultry breeding is the production of fertilized eggs.

Reduced fertility in broiler breeders, particularly after 50 weeks of age, results in significant economic losses in poultry production (Romero-Sánchez, et al., 2008). Studies on aging domestic male birds have revealed a substantial decline in gonadotropic secretions and a reduction in the anterior pituitary gland's production and release of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH) (Abed, & Abdul-Lateef Ali, 2022; Adnan, Ahmad, & Ahmed, 2013; Al-Hassani, & Al-Suhail, 2017; Koch, 2001; Rahim, et al., 2013).

The utilization of naturally occurring plants rich in bioactive compounds has garnered interest for

improving reproductive traits in poultry. Among these, nettle (*Urtica dioica*), a member of the Urticaceae family, is particularly noteworthy due to its diverse phytochemical profile, including polysaccharides, terpenoids, coumarins, and phenylpropanoids (Adnan, Ahmad, & Ahmed, 2013; Yesilbag, & Colpan, 2006). Nettle has been shown to stimulate T lymphocytes, protect liver tissue from damage (Yener, et al., 2009), and act as a potent antioxidant (Costa, Gouveia, & Nobrega, 2002). Studies have also confirmed its ability to inhibit the conversion of testosterone into estrogen (Al-Rubaicy, & Al-Obaidi, 2010). Nettle and its extracts are considered among the safest natural remedies, with a wide range of therapeutic applications and no significant adverse effects (Cırule, et al., 2017). Additionally, nettle roots contain bioactive compounds such as lectins (potent antivirals), scopoline, sterols, fatty acids, polysaccharides, and isolectins (H., & Al-Hassani, 2022).

White tea, derived from the youngest leaves of the *Camellia sinensis* plant before they fully mature, is a rare and valuable type of tea. The leaves are carefully harvested and allowed to dry naturally, preserving their bioactive compounds. White tea has been recognized for its ability to cool the body, stimulate mental alertness, and provide various health benefits due to its rich composition of flavonoids, particularly catechins. It also contains fluoride and several potent antioxidants, including polyphenols, caffeine, methylxanthine, theobromine, and tannic acid, along with vitamins E and C (Chrubasik, et al., 2007; Ekayanti, et al., 2017; Koch, 2001). Furthermore, white tea is a source of manganese, which plays a critical role in protein digestion (Beski, 2019; Hajhashemi, & Klooshani, 2013; Yener, et al., 2009).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of administering nettle (*Urtica dioica*) and white tea (*Camellia sinensis*) leaves on specific reproductive and histological characteristics of rooster testes. These plants were utilized to enhance the reproductive traits of roosters and broiler breeders, particularly to improve fertility (Duncan, 1955; Ezzat, 2023).

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at the College of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Green University, from April 10 to May 22, 2018, for a duration of 42 days. The experiment aimed to evaluate the effects of *Camellia sinensis* (white tea) powder and *Urtica dioica* (nettle) leaf powder on specific reproductive and histological characteristics of the testes in 21 roosters aged 45 weeks. The birds were randomly assigned to seven treatments, with each treatment consisting of three replicates, and one rooster per replicate. The treatment groups were as follows:

the control group received a standard diet without any supplementation, while Treatment 2 was supplemented with 100 mg of white tea powder per kilogram of feed, Treatment 3 with 150 mg of white tea powder per kilogram of feed, and Treatment 4 with 200 mg of white tea powder per kilogram of feed. Similarly, Treatment 5 was supplemented with 100 mg of nettle leaf powder per kilogram of feed, Treatment 6 with 150 mg of nettle leaf powder per kilogram of feed, and Treatment 7 with 200 mg of nettle leaf powder per kilogram of feed. The feed composition was formulated according to the nutritional guidelines provided in the broiler breeder manual (Khishtan, & Beski, 2020).

The study focused on several reproductive and testicular characteristics, including ejaculate volume, sperm concentration, sperm motility, sperm resistance to salt, the percentage of dead sperm, and histological traits of the testes. Tables 1 and 2 show detailed information on the active compounds found in white tea and nettle. Throughout the study, the birds were exposed to a photoperiod of 14 hours of light per day.

Semen Collection and Analysis

Semen was collected from the roosters weekly over six weeks using the method described by Yener, et al. (2009). Microtubes were used for semen collection. Sperm motility was assessed by diluting a 10-microliter semen sample in sodium citrate solution (1:20 dilution). The sample was incubated at 37 °C, placed on a glass slide, covered with a slide cover, and examined under a light microscope equipped with a

camera. Individual sperm motility was evaluated at 40× magnification, while collective sperm motility was assessed at 10× magnification (Al-Salhi, 2020; Ezzat, et al., 2023).

Dead Sperm Estimation

A 10-microliter drop of eosin dye was mixed with an equal volume of semen. The mixture was smeared on a glass slide using another slide at a 45-degree angle. Dead and live sperm were differentiated under a microscope, and 200 sperm were counted per sample in duplicate (Jagadeeswaran Appusamy, 2014).

Sperm Concentration

Sperm concentration was determined using a hemocytometer according to standard procedures.

Histological Examination

Testicular tissues were processed and sectioned for histological examination following the methods described in Ekayanti, et al. (2017), Kuhn, et al. (2004) and Türkdoğan, et al. (2003).

Table 1. Assessment of Biochemical Components of White Tea

Biochemical Components	White tea (Methanolic)	White tea (Aqueous)
Total Polyphenols (%)	35±.01	29±.01
Catechins (%)	19±.01	13±.01
Total Flavonoids (gm/100gm)	5±.001	1±.001
Caffeine (gm/100gm)	4.8±.01	3.9±.01
Tannins (%w/w)	11±.001	9±.001

Source: Chrubasik, et al. (2007)

Table 2. Assessment of Biochemical Components of *Urtica dioica*

Biochemical Components	ml/Mg
Flavonoids	0.2993
Saponins	3.826
Phenols	.8160
Tannins	0.773
Steroids	0.5415
Turbines	0.7891

Source: SPSS (2008)

The effect of various treatments on the traits under investigation was analyzed using a completely randomized design (CRD). Significant differences among the means were determined using Duncan's multiple range test (Vizcarra, Kirby, & Kreider, 2010). All experimental data were statistically analyzed using the SPSS software package, as outlined in (Unachukwu, et al., 2010).

Results and Discussion

Table 3 presents the effects of varying dosages of white tea powder and nettle leaves on selected reproductive traits of broiler breeder roosters. The findings indicate that the fourth, fifth, sixth, and seventh treatments significantly outperformed the other experimental groups in

terms of individual sperm motility, with highly significant differences observed ($p \leq 0.01$). However, there was no significant difference in individual sperm motility between the sixth treatment and the fourth, fifth, or seventh treatments. Additionally, no discernible difference was observed between the third and sixth treatments (SPSS, 2008).

Data in Table 3 shows that there was no significant difference in collective sperm motility between the fourth and fifth treatments or between the sixth and seventh treatments. Moreover, the third treatment did not differ significantly from the other experimental treatments. Notably, the fourth and fifth treatments demonstrated significant superiority ($p \leq 0.01$) over the other treatments in terms of

collective sperm motility. Regarding sperm mass migration, the sixth and seventh treatments were particularly noteworthy, demonstrating significantly better results compared to the control group and other treatments. In contrast, the control and second treatments showed significantly higher percentages of sperm death compared to the other experimental treatments ($p \leq 0.01$). However, all experimental treatments exhibited significant improvements in reducing sperm death rates compared to the control group ($p \leq 0.01$). For sperm resistance to salt, the third, fourth, fifth, and seventh treatments significantly outperformed the control group ($p \leq 0.05$). Meanwhile, the second and sixth treatments did not exhibit significant differences from each other. Regarding sperm concentration, the fourth treatment demonstrated significant superiority over the control group ($p \leq 0.05$), while it did not differ significantly from the second, fifth, sixth, or seventh treatments (Saffari, & Sadrzadeh, 2004; Spinaci, et al., 2018). The superiority of nettle leaf and white tea treatments in most semen characteristics can be attributed to their biologically active compounds with potent

antioxidant properties, particularly flavonoids. These compounds prevent the formation of free radicals, thereby preserving the properties of semen and protecting sperm from damage and death. Consequently, these treatments significantly reduce the percentage of dead sperm and enhance overall semen quality (Mostafa, et al., 2019; Spinaci, et al., 2018; SPSS, 2008). In the second treatment, only 25% of the seminiferous tubules reached the stage of completion in the sperm biosynthesis process, as observed in the histological section presented in the figure.

The diameter of the seminiferous tubules was relatively smaller compared to the other treatments. The tubule walls exhibited normal integrity, without any signs of thickening or damage, and both Sertoli cells and spermatogenic cells appeared normal.

The process of spermatogenesis, which involves the formation of primary and secondary sperm cells, proceeded without abnormalities in this treatment (Gargi, et al., 2017; Giannenas, et al., 2003).

Table 3. The Effect of Adding Different Levels of White Tea Powder and Nettle Leaf on the Semen Characteristics of Broiler Mother's Roosters

Treatments	Sperms Conc. ($\times 10^9$)	Salt Resistance (%) of	Live Sperms (%)	Death Sperms (%)	Collective Movement (%)	Individual Movement (%)
t1	3.050 \pm 0.39 B	73.025 \pm 1.80 B	81.615 \pm 1.29 C	18.380 \pm 1.28 A	77.180 \pm 0.52 C	74.970 \pm 0.47 C
t2	3.435 \pm 0.15 AB	76.915 \pm 0.47 AB	85.220 \pm 0.78 B	14.780 \pm 0.77 B	78.165 \pm 0.28 C	76.770 \pm 1.10 C
t3	3.720 \pm 0.39 AB	78.780 \pm 0.46 A	90.210 \pm 1.67 A	9.785 \pm 1.66 C	80.045 \pm 0.28 BC	77.045 \pm 0.71 BC
t4	4.215 \pm 0.22 A	80.075 \pm 0.42 A	91.720 \pm 0.62 A	8.280 \pm 0.62 C	88.320 \pm 0.44 A	81.655 \pm 0.89 A
t5	3.550 \pm 0.19 AB	79.020 \pm 1.31 A	90.910 \pm 1.02 A	9.090 \pm 1.02 C	87.315 \pm 0.32 A	80.270 \pm 0.29 A
t6	2.945 \pm 0.06 B	76.335 \pm 1.78 AB	89.540 \pm 0.90 A	10.460 \pm 0.90 C	84.570 \pm 3.83 AB	79.940 \pm 1.61 AB
t7	3.530 \pm 0.03 AB	79.275 \pm 0.94 A	90.175 \pm 0.62 A	9.825 \pm 0.62 C	85.220 \pm 0.34 AB	81.270 \pm 0.40 A

Note: NS: Nonsignificant; * $P \leq 0.05$; ** $P \leq 0.01$

Figure 1. Shows a Histological Slice of the Testis Treated with T2

The slides reveals that 60% of the seminiferous tubules reached an advanced stage in the sperm synthesis process. The tubule diameter was larger compared to the second treatment, and the tubule walls remained intact, showing no

signs of thickening or damage. Additionally, both Sertoli cells and Leydig cells appeared normal, indicating proper functioning and structural integrity (Jaiswal, & Lee, 2022; NRC, 1994).

Figure 2. Histological Section of the T3-Treated Testicle

The histological section demonstrates that 60% of the seminiferous tubules have progressed to the stages of sperm production, with their diameters matching those observed in the

control treatment (Chen, H., Yu, C., Wu, H., Li, G., Li, C., Hong, W., Yang, X., Wang, H., & You, X. (2022; NRC). (1994).

Figure 3. Histological Analysis of the Testicle Treated with T4

The histological section shows that approximately 65% of the seminiferous tubules

have reached the stage of complete sperm synthesis. The tubule diameter is comparable to

that observed in the fourth treatment and the control group. The tubule walls exhibit no thickening or damage, and both Sertoli cells and

Leydig cells appear normal (Cabrera, Reyes, & Rafael, 2006; Scanes, Butler, & Kidd, 2020).

Figure 4. Histological Section of the T5-Treated Testicle

The histological section indicates that approximately 75% of the seminiferous tubules have reached the stage of complete sperm synthesis. The diameter of the seminiferous tubules is larger in the fourth and fifth

treatments compared to the control group. Additionally, both Sertoli cells and Leydig cells appear normal (Cabrera, Reyes, & Rafael, 2006; Capcarová, et al., 2014; Friedman, 2007).

Figure 5. Histological Section of the T6 Treated Testicle

The histological section reveals that approximately 20% of the seminiferous tubules have reached the stage of complete sperm synthesis. The diameter of the seminiferous

tubules is smaller compared to the other treatments (Capcarová, et al., 2014; Gargi, et al., 2017; Gülçin, et al., 2004).

Figure 6. Histological Section of the Testis Treated as Control

Conclusion

The addition of nettle leaves and white tea, which contain active ingredients that enhance sperm production, resulted in significant improvements in testicular tissue in the treated groups (NRC, 1994; Rahim, et al., 2013; Romero-Sánchez, et al., 2008).

The findings further demonstrated that the observed enhancements in seminiferous tubule tissue characteristics and daily sperm production can be attributed to elevated testosterone levels and improved efficiency of Sertoli cells (Adnan, Ahmad, & Ahmed, 2013; Al-Ghurairi, Al-Hayani, & Maaeni, 2023; Al-Hassani, et al., 2022).

References

- Abbas, F. R., Ali, N. A. L., Abdul-Jabar, I., & Al-Nassry, A. S. (2019). Effect of adding white tea powder (*Camellia sinensis*) to the Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) birds rations in some traits of blood biochemical and liver enzymes. *Advances in Animal and Veterinary Sciences*, 7(3), 205–209. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17582/journal.aavs/2019/7.3.205.209>
- Abed, R. A., & Abdul-Lateef Ali, A. N. (2022). Effect of supplementation of different levels of *Urtica dioica* seeds to the diet on the immune response and microbial composition of the gastrointestinal tract of broiler chickens. *Archives of Razi Institute*, 77(4), 1371–1375. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22092/ARI.2022.358133.2159>
- Adnan, M., Ahmad, A., & Ahmed, A. (2013). Chemical composition and sensory evaluation of tea (*Camellia sinensis*) commercialized in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 45(3), 901–907. <https://hdl.handle.net/10536/DRO/DU:30086072>
- Ahmed, L. S. (2022). Impact of egg shell and spots colour on the quality of hatching eggs derived from three lines of local quail. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 53(6), 1256–1269. <https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v53i6.1640>
- Al-Ghurairi, R. A. S., Al-Hayani, W. Kh. A., & Maaeni, Y. M. A. (2023). The influence of genistein implantation on offspring sex ratios and their relation to estrogen levels in the blood of Iraqi chickens. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 54(4), 1016–1025. <https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v54i4.1790>
- Al-Hassani, A. S., & Al-Suhail, A. H. (2017). The effect of IGF-1 gene polymorphisms on some physiological and productive parameters in broiler chicken breed Cobb500. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 48(5). <https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v48i5.337>
- Al-Hassani, A. S., Al-Hassani, D. H., & Abdul-Hassan, I. A. (2022). Insulin like growth factor (IGF-2) gene polymorphisms influences certain biochemical parameters in broiler chickens. *Iraqi*

Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 53(5), 1249–1255.
<https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v53i5.1639>

Al-Mahdawi, R. S. (2022). Study the effect of strain measures of post-resuscitate aging and age at slaughter on broiler meat quality. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 53(6), 1512–1524.
<https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v53i6.1667>

Al-Rubaiey, M. G., & Al-Obaidi, F. A. (2010). Effect of experimentally infecting layers with *Listeria monocytogenes* on some blood features. *The Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 34(1), 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.30539/iraqijvm.v34i1.653>

Al-Salhi, A. A. K. (2020). Effect of using water extract of nettle leaf (*Urtica dioica*) on some microbial characteristics of broiler chickens. *University of Thi-Qar Journal of Agriculture Research*, 9(1), 13–23.
<https://doi.org/10.54174/UTJagr.Vo9.N1/02>

Beski, S. M. (2019). Physiological and immunological responses of Japanese quails to oleobiotic. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 49(1). <https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v49i1.221>

Bursill, C., Roach, P. D., Bottema, C. D., & Pal, S. (2001). Green tea upregulates the low-density lipoprotein receptor through the sterol-regulated element binding protein in HepG2 liver cells. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 49, 5639–5645. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf010275d>

Cabrera, C., Reyes, A., & Rafael, G. (2006). Beneficial effects of green tea—A review. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 25(2), 79–99.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.2006.10719518>

Capcarová, M., Kalafová, A., Hrnčár, C., Kopecký, J., & Weis, J. (2014). Comparative analysis of acetic and citric acid on internal milieu of broiler chickens. *Potravinárstvo Slovak Journal of Food Sciences*, 8(1), 190–195.
<https://doi.org/10.5219/379>

Chen, H., Yu, C., Wu, H., Li, G., Li, C., Hong, W., Yang, X., Wang, H., & You, X. (2022). Recent advances in histidine kinase-targeted antimicrobial agents. *Frontiers in Chemistry*, 10, 866392.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2022.866392>

Chrubasik, J. E., Roufogalis, B. D., Wagner, H., & Chrubasik, S. (2007). A comprehensive review on the stinging nettle effect and efficacy profiles. Part II: *Urticae radix*. *Phytomedicine*, 14(7–8), 568–579.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phymed.2007.03.014>

Cirule, D., Krama, T., Krams, R., Elferts, D., Kaasik, A., Rantala, M. J., Mierauskas, P., Luoto, S., & Krams, I. A. (2017). Habitat quality affects stress responses and survival in a bird wintering under extremely low ambient temperatures. *Naturwissenschaften*, 104(11–12), 99.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00114-017-1519-8>

Costa, L. M., Gouveia, S. T., & Nobrega, J. A. (2002). Comparison of heating extraction procedures for Al, Ca, Mg, and Mn in tea samples. *Analytical Sciences*, 18, 313–318.
<https://doi.org/10.2116/analsci.18.313>

Duncan, B. D. (1955). Multiple range and multiple F-test. *Biometrics*, 11, 1–42.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/3001478>

Ekayanti, M., Ardiana, L., Najib, S. Z., Sauriasari, R., & Elya, B. (2017). Pharmacogenetic and phytochemical standardization of white tea leaf (*Camellia sinensis* L. Kuntze) ethanolic extracts. *Pharmacognosy Journal*, 9(2), 221–226.
<https://doi.org/10.5530/pj.2017.2.37>

Ezzat, H. N. (2023). Effect of supplementation fenugreek oil to the diet on the physiological, anatomical, and histological traits of broilers. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 54(1), 106–113.
<https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v54i1.1681>

Ezzat, H. N., Hussein, M. A., Shihab, I. M., & Al-Qazzaz, M. F. A. (2023). Effect of drinking ionized water on histological changes, bacteria count, and some hematological parameters of Japanese quail. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 54(2), 464–471.
<https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v54i2.1721>

Friedman, M. (2007). Overview of antibacterial, antitoxin, antiviral, and antifungal activities of tea flavonoids and teas. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 51, 116–134.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.200600173>

Gargi, S., Sudeshna, S. C., Biswajit, B., & Mohan Kumar, P. (2017). Biochemical and microbiological characterization of white tea.

Journal of Environmental Science, 11(5), 74–80.
<http://doi.org/10.9790/2402-1105037480>

Giannenas, I., Florou-Paneri, P., Papazahariadou, M., Christaki, E., Botsoglou, N. A., & Spais, A. B. (2003). Effect of dietary supplementation with oregano essential oil on performance of broilers after experimental infection with *Eimeria tenella*. *Archiv für Tierernaehrung*, 57(2), 99–106.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0003942031000107292>

Gülçin, I., Küfrevioğlu, O. I., Oktay, M., & Büyükkokuroğlu, M. E. (2004). Antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiulcer, and analgesic activities of nettle (*Urtica dioica* L.). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 90(2–3), 205–215.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2003.09.028>

H., M. A., & Al-Hassani, A. S. (2022). Effect different levels of turmeric root powder to diet on some traits of broiler exposed to heat stress. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 53(4), 950–957.
<https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v53i4.1607>

Hajhashemi, V., & Klooshani, V. (2013). Antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory effects of *Urtica dioica* leaf extract in animal models. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*, 3(2), 193–200.

Hamid, A. F., El-Gendi, G. M., Nihad, A. A., & El-Garhy, O. H. (2020). Effect of adding white tea leaves powder (*Camellia sinensis*) to broiler chicken diets on some biochemical blood parameters. *Annals of Agricultural Sciences, Moshtobor*, 58(4), 941–948.
<https://doi.org/10.21608/assjm.2020.147930>

Jagadeeswaran Appusamy. (2014). Growth promoting potentials of indigenous drugs in broiler chicken. *International Journal of Advanced Veterinary Science and Technology*, 3(1), 93–98.
<http://doi.org/10.23953/cloud.ijavst.191>

Jaiswal, V., & Lee, H. J. (2022). Antioxidant activity of *Urtica dioica*: An important property contributing to multiple biological activities. *Antioxidants*, 11(12), 2494.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11122494>

Khishtan, S., & Beski, S. (2020). Delivery route of chamomile on the growth and subsequent physiology of broiler chickens under *E. coli* challenge. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*,

51(4), 1058–1073.
<https://doi.org/10.36103/ijas.v51i4.1084>

Koch, E. (2001). Extracts from fruits of saw palmetto (*Sabal serrulata*) and roots of stinging nettle (*Urtica dioica*): Viable alternatives in the medical treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia and associated lower urinary tract symptoms. *Planta Medica*, 67(6), 489–500.
<https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2001-16496>

Kuhn, D. J., Burns, A. C., Kazin, A., & Ping-Dou, Q. (2004). Direct inhibition of the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway by ester bond-containing green tea polyphenols is associated with increased expression of sterol regulatory element-binding protein 2 and LDL receptor. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) — Lipids and Lipid Metabolism*, 1682(1–3), 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbailip.2003.12.006>

Mostafa, S. A., Elsyed, I. E., Hassan, A., & Hassan, A. M. (2019). Effect of vitamin E-selenium supplementation on some semen quality traits of Muscovy drakes. *Arab Universities Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 27(2), 1627–1636.
<https://doi.org/10.21608/ajs.2019.12254.1022>

National Research Council (NRC). (1994). *Nutrient requirements of poultry* (9th rev. ed.). National Academy Press.
<https://nap.nationalacademies.org/download/2114>

Rahim, S. M., Taha, E. M., Mubarak, Z. M., Aziz, S. S., Simon, D. K., & Mazlan, A. G. (2013). Protective effect of *Cymbopogon citratus* on hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative stress in the reproductive system of male rats. *Systems Biology in Reproductive Medicine*, 59(6), 329–336.
<https://doi.org/10.3109/19396368.2013.827268>

Romero-Sánchez, H., Plumstead, P. W., Lekrisompong, N., Brannan, K. E., & Brake, J. (2008). Feeding broiler breeder males. 4. Deficient feed allocation reduces fertility and broiler progeny body weight. *Poultry Science*, 87(4), 805–811.
<https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2007-00285>

Saffari, Y., & Sadrzadeh, S. M. (2004). Green tea metabolite EGCG protects membranes against oxidative damage in vitro. *Life Sciences*, 74(12),

1513–1518.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2003.08.019>

Scanes, C. G., Butler, L. D., & Kidd, M. T. (2020). Reproductive management of poultry. In *Animal Agriculture* (pp. 349–366). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817052-6.00020-3>

Spinaci, M., Muccilli, V., Bucci, D., Cardullo, N., Gadani, B., Tringali, C., Tamanini, C., & Galeati, G. (2018). Biological effects of polyphenol-rich extract and fractions from an oenological oak-derived tannin on in vitro swine sperm capacitation and fertilizing ability. *Theriogenology*, *108*, 284–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2017.12.015>

Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). (2008). *Statistical Package for Social Science: User's guide for statistics*.

Türkdoğan, M. K., Özbek, H., Yener, Z., Tuncer, I., Uygan, I., & Ceylan, E. (2003). The role of (*Urtica dioica*) and (*Nigella sativa*) in the prevention of carbon tetrachloride-induced hepatotoxicity in rats. *Phytotherapy Research*, *17*(8), 942–946. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.1266>

Unachukwu, U. J., Ahmed, S., Kavalier, A., Lyles, J. T., & Kennelly, E. J. (2010). White and green teas (*Camellia sinensis* var. *sinensis*): Variation in phenolic, methylxanthine, and antioxidant profiles. *Journal of Food Science*, *75*(6),

C541–C548. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2010.01705.x>

Vizcarra, J. A., Kirby, J. D., & Kreider, D. L. (2010). Testis development and gonadotropin secretion in broiler breeder males. *Poultry Science*, *89*(2), 328–334. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2009-00286>

Wang, H., Provan, G. J., & Helliwell, K. (2000). Tea flavonoids: their functions, utilization and analysis. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, *11*, 152–160. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244\(00\)00061-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2244(00)00061-3)

Wang, Y., & Ho, C. T. (2009). Polyphenolic chemistry of tea and coffee: a century of progress. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *57*(18), 8109–8114. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf804025c>

Yener, Z., Celik, I., Ilhan, F., & Bal, R. (2009). Effects of (*Urtica dioica* L.) seed on lipid peroxidation, antioxidants, and liver pathology in aflatoxin-induced tissue injury in rats. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, *47*(2), 418–424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2008.11.031>

Yesilbag, D., & Colpan, I. (2006). Effects of organic acid supplemented diets on growth performance, egg production and quality, and on serum parameters in laying hens. *Revue de Médecine Vétérinaire*, *157*, 280–284. https://www.revmedvet.com/2006/RMV157_280_284.pdf